

Investigating the Determinants of Mutual Funds Investment Decision: Evidence from Earning Professionals of Bangladesh

Afrin Rahman Mili¹ | Md. Gulam Kibria ACA²

The Authors are:

¹Lecturer

Department of Business Administration
Dhaka International University

²Associate Member of the

Institute of Chartered Accountants
of Bangladesh (ICAB)

The article was reviewed by
Muhammed Farhad Hussain FCA

Abstract

Surveying 105 respondents with at least bachelor's degrees and earnings, this study aims to identify the determinants influencing investors to invest in mutual funds. Compared to other South Asian countries like India and Pakistan, the development of mutual funds in Bangladesh is not in a significant stage. Based on Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), this study has done the socio-demographic analysis, sampling adequacy test through KMO and Bartlett's Test, validity and reliability test through Cronbach's Alpha, Exploratory Factor Analysis (Extracting factors through Eigenvalues, scree plot, rotated factor matrix). The findings of the SEM model show that investors emphasize risk and return factors, and they are risk-averse investors. Reduced risk, better return, regular income, capital appreciation, liquidity, diversification of investment and long-term income features appeal to investors to invest in mutual funds.

Keywords

Financial Awareness (FA), Risk-Return Perception (RRP), Investment attitude (IA), Mutual Fund Investment Decision

Introduction

To keep pace with the monetary value of inflation, investment is a strategy for fund owners to increase their fund value. It is a

general principle of finance not to put all the eggs in a single basket. The underlying meaning of this principle is to diversify the investment in various assets to minimize risk which investment in mutual funds satisfies. As mutual fund investment is managed by professionals, investors who have limited knowledge and time to understand and monitor investment can get the advantage of investing in mutual funds. Having so much convenience, still mutual fund investment is not popular in our country.

In India, almost 10% of people invest in mutual funds (Singal and Manrai, 2018). In 2022, the mutual fund investment amount in Pakistan was 57 thousand 800 crores Tk. compared to 10 thousand 948 crore Tk. investment in Bangladesh. According to USA based Verified Market Research® Institute, the total worldwide mutual funds investment amount is 72.79 trillion dollars whereas out of this total investment, 32.96 trillion-dollar investment is comprised by the United States (Source: <https://samakal.com/feature/article/2307186259/>). It depicts that mutual fund investment is a popular term in developed countries and also becoming popular in South Asian countries like India and Pakistan. In Bangladesh, the government-owned investment institute 'Investment Corporation of Bangladesh' launched the first mutual fund of Bangladesh on 25th April

1980. According to the statistics of DSE as of 30 September 2024, there are 37 listed mutual funds in Bangladesh (Source: https://www.dsebd.org/ltp_industry.php?area=12). The mutual fund market in Bangladesh is quite small. The reason behind the poor investment scenario in Bangladesh may account for lacking financial awareness, trust issues, poor governance, and unrest in the stock market.

The market price of mutual funds is fixed by demand and supply factors whereas the intrinsic value of mutual funds is fixed by NAV. During the calculation of NAV, the closing price of the securities in the fund's portfolio is considered. As the market price is determined based on the demand and supply factors, NAV is not always equal to the market price (Chowdhury et al.,

2018). Although NAV is guided by the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission to measure the performance of mutual funds, Sharpe ratio, Treynor ratio and Jensen's Alpha are also used by globally and locally to assess the performance of funds (Anwar et al., 2016). The importance of mutual funds in Bangladesh's capital markets is growing day by day as Bangladesh's economy has faced lots of challenges recently including higher interest rates, lower foreign reserves, and the impulsive nature of the capital market. The mutual fund can not only develop the capital market but also contribute to the money market as it can act as an inter-mediation in the financial industry (Begum et al., 2016).

There are plenty of spaces or gaps to work on to understand

the factors that distract investors from investing in mutual funds and to focus on factors that can influence investors to invest in mutual funds. The principal objective of this paper is to find out the factors that determine mutual fund investment decisions taken by investors. It will deliver a message to the growing and new mutual fund companies about which factors need to be fostered in designing the scheme to achieve the expected growth in the mutual fund sector.

Literature Review

Dhar et al. (2017) defined a mutual fund as a pool of funds collected by a company from investors to invest in securities like stocks, and bonds. Mutual fund investment is a capital market investment managed by the professional fund manager. A mutual fund allows investors to diversify their risks as professional fund managers do not concentrate the investment on a single security. A mutual fund allows small investors to participate in diversified investments where a company sells shares of mutual funds and the proceeds from selling shares invest in diversified securities. Being managed by professionals, the mutual fund generates better returns bearing lower risks. Mungai (2021) asserted that mutual fund investment is indispensable for a country's financial and economic growth by including numerous people in the investment mechanism in

Investigating the Determinants of Mutual Funds Investment Decision: Evidence from Earning Professionals of Bangladesh

the capital market. The performance of mutual funds depends on the fund-raising company's ability to generate capital gains, dividends or interest within the mentioned period.

Surveying 100 respondents, Saha and Dey (2011) outlined the factors like financial awareness, preference, and expectation that influence investors in deciding whether to invest in mutual funds. According to Singal and Manrai (2018), mutual fund aims to maximize return and lower the risk. Investing in mutual funds minimizes risk through investment diversification. But

investors may also doubt whether the fund manager works well on behalf of them. Investment in mutual funds is influenced by economic, sociological and psychological factors. Fundamental factors like risk, return, and liquidity influence investors significantly in making investment decisions for mutual funds. Arathy et al., (2015) stated that for risk-averse investors mutual funds are a lucrative option as it is less risky compared to investing in the share market directly. The study found that tax benefits, diversification, capital appreciation, and brand image shape the investment decision of investors in the case

of investing in mutual funds. The authors also outlined that knowledge and knowledge about mutual funds to retail investors is possible through consultancy of brokers, financial institutions, and advertisements. According to Vyas (2013), mutual fund companies should come forward to provide advisory services to investors and ensure transparency of transaction-related information. This concept is further illustrated by Mohindroo and Singh (2013). The authors affirmed that fund managers can upgrade the performance of mutual funds by analyzing investor behavior and providing them with the proper service.

Shira et al., (2017) investigated risk-return perception, financial awareness, investment criteria, and socio-demographic data to identify the factors that influence mutual fund investment decisions.

Based on the findings from the discussed literature review, this research will investigate the following hypotheses:

H1: There is a significant association between financial awareness and mutual fund investment decisions.

H2: There is a significant association between risk-return perception and mutual fund investment decisions.

H3: There is a significant association between

investment attitude and mutual fund investment decisions.

Methodology

The respondents of this study include both mutual fund investors and non-mutual fund investors in Bangladesh. The questionnaire was prepared in Google form and sent directly to the respondents using social media. The research population included all the distinguished working professionals who have a minimum bachelor's degree. Education and profession have been considered as key factors before collecting data from respondents as the mutual fund is still an emerging concept in Bangladesh and earnings are also required to invest in somewhere. The sample size is an important consideration in data analysis. According to

(Westland, 2010), 10 observations per indicator was considered as a rule of thumb by previous researchers to consider a data set adequate. For this study, A-priori Sample Size Calculator for Structural Equation Models has been used considering anticipated effect size (0.3 has been used here for medium effect), desired statistical power level (0.80), number of latent variables (4), number of observed variables (16) and probability level (0.05). The outcome showed that a minimum of 100 sample size is required to create the model structure. This study has collected 107 responses initially.

To ensure the reliability of the data set, this research examines whether the data set is unengaged. The mean and standard deviation of each respondent's responses individually have been calculated. If any mean value is less than 0.5 or more than 4.5 and if any respondent's standard deviation is less than 0.25, it means the respondent has ticked all 1 or all 5 or the same answer for every question. Two responses for such an issue have been deleted and then the data set for analysis contained 105 responses.

A 5-point Likert scale has been used to measure the items where Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, and Strongly Agree = 5. The key variables and measurement items have been exhibited in Table 1:

**Investigating the Determinants of Mutual Funds Investment Decision:
Evidence from Earning Professionals of Bangladesh**

Table 1: Summary of Measurement Items

Construct	Item	Source
Financial Awareness (FA)	FA1: I am not aware that mutual fund investment is managed by professional fund managers who have specialized skills and experience.	Saha and Dey (2011)
	FA2: Only experts can invest in mutual funds	Shira et al., (2017)
	FA3: Only large amounts of money can be invested in mutual funds	Saha and Dey (2011)
	FA4: It's not known to me that mutual fund generates better returns bearing lower risks, and reduce the risk associated with an investment portfolio through investing in different categories of securities.	Dhar et al., (2017), Arathy et al., (2015)
	FA5: I am not aware that mutual fund investors can enjoy an annual tax rebate.	Shira et al., (2017)
Investment Attitude (IA)	IA1: I prefer investment in Bank fixed Deposit to mutual fund	Shira et al., (2017)
	IA2: I prefer investment in stock/bond to mutual fund	Shira et al., (2017)
	IA3: I choose investment considering net asset value (NAV)	Chowdhury et al., (2018)
Risk-Return Perception (RRP)	RRP1: I prefer investments where there is reduced risk and better return.	Arathy et al., (2015)
	RRP2: I prefer regular income investment	Shira et al., (2017)
	RRP3: I prefer long-term capital appreciation investment.	Arathy et al., (2015)
	RRP4: I prefer an investment that provides liquidity.	Singal and Manrai (2018)
	RRP5: I consider an investment safe when it is managed by professionals and can generate higher income compared to other long-term investments.	Singal and Manrai (2018)
Mutual Fund Investment Decision (MFID)	MFID1: I have not invested in a mutual fund as I have not found significant promotional activities for it in Bangladesh.	Arathy et al., (2015)
	MFID2: In future, I want to invest in a mutual fund as it offers better returns with reduced risk along with capital appreciation, liquidity and tax-rebate benefits.	Singal and Manrai (2018)
	MFID3: I think initiatives need to be taken by banks and Mobile Financial Services to make mutual fund investment more popular.	Vyas (2013), Mohindroo and Singh (2013)

Figure 1 exhibits a structural equation model based on which the hypotheses will be investigated.

Figure 1: SEM model

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26.

Structural equation modelling (SEM) will be used to find out the association between endogenous or dependent variable (here, Mutual Fund Investment Decision) and exogenous variables or independent variables (here, Financial Awareness, Investment Attitude, Risk-Return Perception). IBM SPSS AMOS 26 software will be used to investigate the determinants of mutual fund investment decisions.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Figure 2 exhibits the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Among 105 respondents, 70.48% were male and 29.52% were female. 63.81% of respondents belong to the age group of 22 years to 30 years. The minimum education criteria of respondents were a bachelor's degree and 64.76% have a BBA/MBA degree, indicating that most of the respondents have heard about mutual funds. There is a mixed group of professions. 30.48% of respondents are bankers, 22.86% are practicing professional accountants, 16.19% are other private service holders, 14.29% are govt. service holders and 12.38% are academics. Among the respondents, 67.62% fall into the income group of BDT100000 to BDT800000.

**Investigating the Determinants of Mutual Funds Investment Decision:
Evidence from Earning Professionals of Bangladesh**

Figure 2: Socio-demographic profile of respondents

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test for assessing sampling adequacy

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling is calculated to measure the sampling adequacy. The benchmark for KMO is 0.50. When the KMO test results in 0.50 or more than 0.50, it indicates that sampling adequacy is satisfactory. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity examines whether the correlation matrix is an identity matrix. The null hypothesis is that the correlation matrix is the identity matrix. The presence of an identity matrix indicates that variables are unrelated and thus unsuitable for structure detection.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.826
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	590.151
	df	120
	Sig.	.000

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26.

Table 2 exhibits that KMO test results in 0.826 which is much higher than the benchmark of 0.50 indicating adequate sample adequacy of the data in this research. Here, the P value of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is less than 0.05 which indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected, and the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix. Thus, the variables of this study are related and suitable for structure detection.

Table 3: Cronbach's Alpha for testing validity and reliability

Description	Cronbach's Alpha
Financial Awareness	0.807
Investment Attitude	0.604
Risk Return Perception	0.831
Mutual Fund Investment Decision	0.728

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26

Measuring the reliability and validity of the data set is a prerequisite to move on to further calculation. To check the internal consistency, reliability and validity of the data set, Cronbach's Alpha is calculated. According to Tavakol and Dennick (2011), Internal consistency means whether all the items under a construct measure the same concept. The interrelatedness of the items under a construct is required to have a reliable and valid data set. According to Saunders (2009), the acceptable range for Cronbach's Alpha is 0.60 to 0.70 in the case of exploratory research. All the constructs under Cronbach's alpha are higher than 0.60 indicating a reliable and valid construct.

Table 4: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)-Extracting factors through Eigenvalues

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Total Variance Explained			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.752	29.699	29.699	4.191	26.191	26.191	2.829	17.681	17.681
2	2.763	17.269	46.968	2.306	14.411	40.601	2.443	15.269	32.950
3	1.420	8.872	55.840	.796	4.974	45.575	1.501	9.379	42.329
4	1.047	6.542	62.383	.702	4.389	49.964	1.222	7.635	49.964
5	.784	4.897	67.280						
6	.728	4.549	71.829						
7	.671	4.192	76.021						
8	.603	3.769	79.790						
9	.561	3.509	83.299						
10	.528	3.299	86.598						
11	.455	2.847	89.444						
12	.416	2.603	92.047						
13	.386	2.412	94.459						
14	.354	2.213	96.672						
15	.304	1.901	98.573						
16	.228	1.427	100.000						

Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26

Investigating the Determinants of Mutual Funds Investment Decision: Evidence from Earning Professionals of Bangladesh

In the methodology of this research, the structural equation model presents 4 constructs (Financial awareness, investment attitude, risk-return perception, and mutual fund investment decision). This research has used 16 items under 4 constructs. Exploratory factor analysis is done to decide how many factors to be retained in the analysis based on eigenvalues (Iantovics, et al., 2019). The eigenvalue is a measure of how much of the variance of the observed variables a variable explains. Any factor with an eigenvalue greater than or equal to 1 explains more variance. Here according to calculation through SPSS, factors 1, 2, 3 and 4 are identified as the best factors as these 4 have eigenvalue greater than 1. As this study has used 4 constructs named financial awareness, investment attitude, risk-return perception, and mutual fund investment decision, the extraction of 4 factors justifies the model construction of this study.

Figure 3: Scree plot

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26

The scree plot is the graphical representation of the factors extracted through eigenvalues. Among the 16 items, 4 items having eigenvalues greater than 1 further justify this study's model development of 4 constructs (Financial awareness, investment attitude, risk-return perception, and mutual fund investment decision).

Table 5: Rotated Factor Matrix

	Factor 1 Risk Return perception	Factor 2 Financial Awareness	Factor 3 Mutual Fund Investment Decision	Factor 4 Investment Attitude
RRP1	.673			
RRP2	.732			
RRP3	.543			
RRP4	.752			
RRP5	.656			
FA1		.697		
FA2		.721		
FA3		.714		
FA4		.652		
FA5		.585		
MFID1			.473	
MFID2			.556	
MFID3			.773	
IA1				.665
IA2				.607
IA3				.399

Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.
a. 4 factors extracted. 8 iterations required.

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26

Table 5 shows the result of the rotated factor matrix. This study has used 16 items and 4 constructs. The rotated factor matrix illustrated that those 16 items have been clustered under 4 factors that are considered determinants regarding investment decisions in mutual funds by investors. The first factor (risk-return perception) comprised 5 items (reduced risk and better return, regular income investment, long-term capital appreciation investment, liquidity, preferring professionals' management and higher income compared to other long-term investments). The second factor (Financial Awareness) carries 5 items (not aware that mutual fund investment is managed by professionals, only experts' investment in mutual funds, only large amounts of investment, better returns bearing lower risks, and annual tax rebate). The third factor (Mutual Fund Investment Decision) contains 3 items (not invested in a mutual fund as not found significant promotional activities in Bangladesh, in future-want to invest in a mutual fund, initiatives need to be taken by banks and Mobile Financial Services to make mutual fund investment more popular). The fourth factor (Investment Attitude) comprised 3 items ((Bank fixed Deposit) to the mutual fund, investment in stock/bond to mutual fund, and investment considering net asset value (NAV)).

**Investigating the Determinants of Mutual Funds Investment Decision:
Evidence from Earning Professionals of Bangladesh**

Figure 4: Findings of Structural Equation Model (SEM)

Source: Authors' contribution based on the output developed by IBM SPSS Statistics 26.

Table 6: Structural model

Hypothesis	Path	Beta/estimates	P	Comment
H1	Financial Awareness > Mutual Fund Investment Decision	-0.04	0.656	Rejected
H2	Risk return perception > Mutual Fund Investment Decision	0.77	0.000	Accepted
H3	Investment Attitude > Mutual Fund Investment Decision	0.29	0.184	Rejected

This research has found a significant association between the risk-return perception of mutual fund investors and their investment decisions in mutual funds. Whenever investors consider whether they will invest in mutual funds, they look for reduced risk, better return and liquidity. Investors want to be assured whether mutual funds will provide regular income investment. No significant association has been found between financial awareness, investment attitude and mutual fund investment decisions. The mutual fund that provides capital appreciation, diversification, long long-term higher income is expected to be attractive to potential investors.

Fund managers of mutual funds may design their schemes in a way that provides reduced risk, better return, regular income,

capital appreciation, liquidity, diversification of investment and long-term income. The news of these designed schemes needs to reach prospective investors through advertisements, promotions, financial institutions, internet.

The significant association between risk-return perception and mutual fund investment decisions also indicates the risk-averse characteristics of the investors. Investors seek to rely on professional fund managers as they have limited time and lack of in-depth knowledge which professional fund managers need to keep in mind in designing the schemes. In the case of designing further schemes of mutual funds, companies may focus on these risk-averse investment criteria in-depth.

Chapter Five: Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has indicated two components that are considered more important by investors who want to decide on whether to invest in mutual fund, one is risk and another one is return. Considering the risk-averse perception of investors, new or growing staged mutual fund companies may emphasize lower risk, better return, long-term higher but regular income, liquidity, capital appreciation and diversification characteristics in designing the mutual fund scheme. This study will add value in this field to take steps to influence investors to invest in mutual funds. However, we observe some pervasive challenges like the extension of tenure of closed-end funds after expiry without unitholders' consent; poor fund management capabilities of most fund managers; investment in non-listed companies at abnormally high valuation; and poorly performing capital market and speculative nature of the market.

It is evident from the beta of risk-return perception and its significant level that the investors invest in mutual funds very defensively as the mutual fund industry in Bangladesh is still in the growing phase. The mutual fund industry of Bangladesh needs to address regulatory, operational, and investor-related challenges to improve investor confidence as

Investigating the Determinants of Mutual Funds Investment Decision: Evidence from Earning Professionals of Bangladesh

well as the growth of the industry. For regulatory improvement, strengthening regulation and oversight is required from the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC) to ensure transparency, good governance, and investor protection. Investor education and awareness are prerequisites for making any kind of investment decision. To enlighten the investors of Bangladesh, the government and regulators need to conduct a nationwide campaign, workshop, and training on mutual funds.

The limitation of this study is that the number of respondents may need to be increased to get a wider conclusion from the whole market. For further similar research, researchers may arrange a focus group discussion (FGD) to have direct opinion from prospective and current mutual fund investors in precedence of preparing the questionnaire.

References

Anwar, S.R. and Arif, T.M.H., 2016. Evaluation of mutual funds performance in Bangladesh: Investors and market perspective. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 16(9), pp.1-10.

Arathy, B., Nair, A.A., Sai, A. and Pravitha, N.R., 2015. A Study on factors affecting investment on mutual funds and its preference

of retail investors. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 5(8), pp.1-4.

Begum, N.N. and Rahman, S., 2016. An Analytical Study on Investors Preference towards Mutual Fund Investment: A Study in Dhaka City, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(10), pp.184-191.

Chowdhury, T.S., Habibullah, M. and Nahar, N., 2018. Risk and return analysis of closed-end mutual fund in Bangladesh. *Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance Research*, 3(2), pp.83-92.

Dhar, S., Salema, S.K. and Saha, A., 2017. Factors affecting individual investor behavior: empirical evidence from mutual fund investors in Dhaka city. *Management*, 31(3&4), pp.79-101.

<https://samakal.com/feature/article/2307186259/>

https://www.dsebd.org/ltp_industry.php?area=12

Mohindroo, A. and Singh, S., 2013. Factors affecting investment in mutual funds-An exploratory study. *SAARJ Journal on Banking & Insurance Research*, 2(3), pp.1-24.

Mungai, C., 2021. Effect of Economic Growth on Performance of Mutual Trust

Funds in Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).

Saha, S. and Dey, M., 2011. Analysis of Factors Affecting Investors' Perception of Mutual Fund Investment. *IUP Journal of Management Research*, 10(2).

Shira, M.J., Murhadi, W.R. and Sutejo, B.S., 2017. Determinants Of Mutual funds Investment Behavior. *Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 16(1).

Singal, V.S. and Manrai, R., 2018. Factors Affecting Investment in Mutual Funds. *Journal of general management research*, 5(2).

Tavakol, M. and Dennick, R., 2011. Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International journal of medical education*, 2, p.53.

Vyas, R., 2013. Factors influencing investment decision in mutual funds (with special reference to Indore city). *ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*, 3(7), pp.276-290.

Westland, J.C., 2010. Lower bounds on sample size in structural equation modeling. *Electronic commerce research and applications*, 9(6), pp.476-487.